

in highly sensitive varieties. Weather records for February 1976 show a low minimum temperature of 9.7° C and an

average minimum temperature of 13.9° C. But no sudden fall in minimum temperature was recorded which possi-

bly explains why such severe cold injury symptoms had not been observed before. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Fungicide control of rice grain infection

K. Govindarajan and S. Kannaiyan, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

Grain infection caused by seed-borne fungal pathogens *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Acrocyli-drium oryzae*, and *Curvularia* sp. is a serious problem when crop ripening stage coincides with the monsoon. The effect of fungicides on the control of grain infection in IR20 was studied under wet field conditions.

Fungicides were sprayed twice, once at the milky stage and again a week

Effect of fungicides on grain infection and yield, Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Application/ha ^a	Grain infection	Grain yield
Copper oxychloride 50% WP	1250 g	15.1	3.40
Edifenphos 50% EC	750 ml	14.6	3.39
Carbendazim 50% WP 500	g	16.7	3.35
Carboxin 75% WP	500 g	16.8	3.29
Mancozeb 75% WP	1250 g	17.1	3.28
Cuman-L 50% EC	1250 ml	17.0	3.27
Captafol 80% WP	750 g	17.0	3.13
Unsprayed control	—	17.3	3.18
C.D.		0.8	ns

^aEach application.

later. Control plots were sprayed with plain water. Infected grains in 5 ran-domly selected clumps were assessed at

harvest. Plots treated with edifenphos and copper oxychloride had the lowest grain infection (see table). ■

Rotten disease of azolla

Parkpian Arunyanart, Arunee Surin, Wan-chai Rochanahasadin, and Somkid Distha-porn, Rice Pathology Branch (RPB), Divi-sion of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Bangkok, Thailand

Paddy soils in northeast Thailand are more suitable for azolla propagation than soils in other regions. But azolla there has been damaged by an unknown disease.

Disease samples were collected at the RPB during September-November 1981. Two genera of fungi were isolated. One genus showed a whitish colony of small mycelium, the other a cream brown colony of larger mycelium. Both were grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA). The whitish small mycelium was found to be the causal agent of the symptoms of rotten disease on azolla. The fungus belongs to the genus *Myrothecium*. Its general morphology is:

— Hyaline septate mycelium, 2.5-3.8

1. Sporodochia of *Myrothecium* fungus causing rotten disease of azolla in Thailand.

× 10.3-30 μ, good growth on PDA. Conidiophores macronem-

atous, mononematous, closely packed together to form sporodo-

chia (see Fig. 1, 2). Branched, with apical branches arranged penicillately, straight or flexuous, colorless or olivaceous, smooth or verruculose.

—Conidiogenous cells monophialidic, discrete, cylindrical, clavate or subulate. Conidia aggregated in dark green or black, slimy masses semi-endogenous or acrogenous, simple, cylindrical with rounded ends, navicular, limoniform or broadly ellipsoidal, often with a projecting truncate base, hyaline to pale olive, smooth or striately marked O-septate.

The conidia found are similar to those of *Myrothecium verrucaria*, which are navicular, limoniform or broadly ellipsoidal, slightly protuberant and truncate at the base, distinctly colored, 6-10 × 2-

2. Conidia of *Myrothecium* fungus causing rotten disease of azolla in Thailand.

4.5 μ.

Infected azolla turns brown, then rapidly rots and dies. The disease symptoms are spotted with distinct white fun-

gus mycelium. In favorable conditions, the disease develops and spreads so rapidly that all azolla in a pond 4 × 8 m can be killed in a few days. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Mites infesting rice in Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh, India

A. Venugopalarao, assistant entomologist, Sugarcane Research Station, Anakapalle; A. K. Sanyal, zoologist, Acarology Section, Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta; and T. Ramamohan Rao, assistant research officer, Sugarcane Research Station, Anakapalle, India

Leaves of rice varieties Mypali, Sannabayyahunda, Ramasagaralu, and Phalguna cultivated around Anakapalle were found to have brown streaks (dried tissue) between veins and tears parallel to veins, giving a gale-torn appearance. Two species of mites responsible for the damage were identified by the Zoological Survey of India: *Schelorbates zealandicus*, family Oribatulidae, suborder Cryptostigmata, and *Oloaelaps holaspis*, family Laelaptidae, suborder Mesostigmata.

The oribatid mites are dark brown and round and appear as minute dust particles on a white background. The laelaptid mites are brown and oblong. They feed on the tissues between leaf

veins and hide in the hollow places in the fed parts.

The mites were found to be existing on a grass species (under identification) growing on the bunds of rice fields. Their occurrence was mostly due to favorable weather during the early southwest monsoon with intermittent rainy periods. No insecticides had been applied to the crop. ■

Larval parasites of rice leaffolder in southern Sri Lanka

Rohan H. S. Rajapakse and Varuni L. Kulasekare, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Ruhuna University College, Matara, Sri Lanka

A major outbreak of rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenee) was observed in the primary cultivation season April-July 1981. Characteristic damage included leaf skeletonization, giving a scorched appearance to the borders and shaded areas of the field in the early part of the season.

In a study to identify larval parasites

regulating leaffolder populations in southern Sri Lanka, five parasites were found: *Apanteles ruficrus* (Haliday) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), *Apanteles flavipes* (Cameron) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), *Microbracon hebetor* Say (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), *Elasmus* spp. (Hymenoptera: Elasmidae), and *Bactromyia franssoni* Bar. (Diptera: Tachinidae). Parasitization of leaffolder larvae was 48% in Kamburupitiya, 53% in Matara, 60% in Hakmana, 38% in Denipitiya, and 70% in Mapalana. Disruption of the leaffolder parasite complex by periodic insecticide spraying to control brown planthoppers and stem borers may have resulted in the outbreak. ■

Major insect pests of rice on hilly tracts of Uttar Pradesh, India

D. K. Garg and J. P. Tandon, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture, ICAR, Almora, Uttar Pradesh, India

Systematic field surveys have been carried out since 1977 to identify the pest